

On the Biogenesis of the Carbazoles of Rutaceae

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Since the report of the structure on murrayanine¹ (I) the first member of a new group of carbazole alkaloids, the isolation of several members of this group, glycozoline² (II), glycozolidine³ (III), heptaphylline⁴ (IV), ginimbirine⁵ (V), murrayacine⁶ (VI), mukoeic acid⁷ (VII) have been reported besides those with partially known structures, mahanimbine⁸ (VIII) and isomahanimbine⁹ (IX). These compounds have been found to occur in taxonomically related genera of plants (*Murraya*, *Glycosmis*, *Clausena*) of the family *Rutaceae*. From the occurrence of the alkaloids derived from the anthranilic acid¹⁰ as also the carbazoles in the family *Rutaceae*, the anthranilate origin of the latter was suggested by the present author¹¹. The co-occurrence of furoquinoline bases and glycozoline and glycozolidine in *Glycosmis pentaphylla*^{2a} may be considered as circumstantial evidence in favour of this idea.

- (i) R₁ = -OCH₃, R₃ = -CHO, R₂ = R₄ = R₅ = H (v) R₁ = -CH₃
(ii) R₃ = -CH₃, R₅ = -OCH₃, R₁ = R₂ = R₄ = H (vi) R₁ = -CHO
(iii) R₂ = R₄ = -OCH₃, R₅ = -CH₃, R₁ = R₃ = H
(iv) R₁ = -CH₂-CH=C $\begin{matrix} \text{CH}_3 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C} \\ \diagup \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{matrix}$, R₄ = -OH,
R₃ = -CHO, R₄ = R₅ = H
(vii) R₁ = -OCH₃, R₃ = -COOH, R₂ = R₄ = R₅ = H

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The ready photolytic or thermal cyclisation of diphenylamine to carbazole and the synthesis of glycozoline¹² by photocyclisation of 4-methoxy-4'-methyl diphenylamine provide a background for the concept of diphenylamine origin of the carbazoles of *Rutaceae*. In the light of the mechanistic and biogenetic explanation of N-phenylation of anthranilic acid by Leete¹³, the formation of carbazole from anthranilic acid via diphenylamine derivative could be portrayed as follows. (Scheme 1)

SCHEME I

Since no diphenylamine has been reported from plant sources and N-phenylated anthranilic acid derivatives are rare, the hypothesis lacks substantial circumstantial support.

Recent work on the biosynthesis of indole bases with C₇ skeleton¹⁴ and some anthraquinones¹⁵ show that one of the aromatic rings in these compounds may be a contribution of the mevalonate pathway. The skeletal units of all the carbazoles cited show that besides an anthranilate unit, they have an aromatic fragment having five carbon residue. It is quite conceivable that one of the aromatic rings in carbazole originate from mevalonate unit. In all these carbazoles, 3-position the most active centre of electrophilic attack of the carbazole nucleus which is occupied by methyl, formyl or carboxy groups. This suggests that the formation of carbazole nucleus precedes⁷ C-methylation or formylation. Recent demonstration of aromatic C-methylation¹⁶ of aniline with methionine supports this view. The methyl group may subsequently undergo oxidation to an aldehyde and carboxylic group. The idea of the incorporation of a C₁-unit to carbazole nucleus stands against the mevalonate origin of one of the aromatic ring.

The formation of pyran ring could be rationalised by the contribution of a mevalonate unit as has been found in many phenolics¹⁷ with such an unit. Heptaphylline girinimbine and murrayacine are typical phenolics with modified C₅-unit.

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The diphenylamine hypothesis appears to be attractive as it envisages a common biogenetic route to the acridones and carbazoles of *Rutaceae*. The co-occurrence of both the species of compounds in the genus *Glycosmis* stands in its support. It may be pointed out that Hughes and Ritchie¹⁸ conceived that acridones arise by condensation of a *o*-amino-benzaldehyde or its equivalent and a phloroglucinol or its equivalent unit whereas Leete¹³ believes the formation of acridones from an anthranilate unit and three acetate units.

The future experimentation on the biosynthesis or isolation of diphenylamine derivatives may throw further light on the ontogeny of carbazoles of *Rutaceae*.

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